

PREVALENCE, AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS EXCLUSIVE BREASTFEEDING AMONG MOTHERS

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Abstract

Background: Exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) is globally recognized as the optimal method of infant feeding for the first six months of life, providing essential nutrients and protection against infections while promoting healthy growth and development. Despite strong recommendations by the World Health Organization (WHO), the prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding remains below global targets in many developing countries, including Pakistan. Maternal knowledge and attitudes play a significant role in influencing breastfeeding practices.

Objectives: To assess the prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding among mothers of infants aged 0–12 months

Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study aimed to assess the prevalence and maternal attitudes toward exclusive breastfeeding among mothers of infants aged 0–12 months attending Civil Hospital Nawabshah. A total of 188 mothers were selected through non-probability convenience sampling. Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire consisting of three sections: demographic characteristics, breastfeeding practices based on 24-hour recall, and a maternal attitude scale toward exclusive breastfeeding. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25, and results were presented in frequencies and percentages.

Results: The findings revealed that only 44.1% of mothers reported breastfeeding during the previous day, while 50% had introduced formula feeding, indicating a high prevalence of mixed feeding practices. Although early introduction of water, animal milk, and soft foods was comparatively low, it still contradicted WHO recommendations. Despite inadequate practice, the majority of mothers demonstrated a positive attitude toward exclusive breastfeeding. Most participants acknowledged that exclusive breastfeeding improves bonding, supports child growth and development, is easily digested, and is convenient and economical.

Conclusion: The study concludes that although maternal attitudes toward exclusive breastfeeding were largely positive, the actual prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding was insufficient. Strengthening postnatal counseling, family

education, and continuous breastfeeding support is essential to bridge the gap between knowledge and practice and to improve exclusive breastfeeding rates in urban communities.

INTRODUCTION

Exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) for the first six months of life is globally recognized as the optimal method of infant nutrition by the world health organization. It provides complete nutrition, strengthens immunity, and fosters mother-child bonding. Despite its benefits, EBF rates remain suboptimal in many regions due to sociocultural, economic, and educational barriers.

Recent studies have emphasized the importance of accurate measurement and contextual understanding of EBF practices. Refined indicators for assessing EBF prevalence using household survey data have revealed significant variation across countries, underscoring the need for localized strategiesⁱ. Maternal knowledge, positive attitudes, and sociodemographic factors such as education level, income, and delivery method—have been identified as key determinants of EBF adherenceⁱⁱ.

In urban Pakistani settings, mothers often face unique challenges including limited maternity leave, exposure to formula marketing, and lack of institutional support, these factors may contribute to suboptimal EBF rates, despite increasing awareness campaigns. Understanding maternal attitudes and the prevalence of EBF in such contexts is essential for designing targeted interventions that align with sustainable development goal, which aims to reduce preventable deaths of newborns and children under fiveⁱⁱⁱ.

The covid-19 pandemic further disrupted breastfeeding support systems, reducing access to healthcare and increasing misinformation^{iv}. However, community-based interventions and peer counseling have shown promise in improving EBF adherence during this period. Cultural beliefs and family dynamics also play a critical role in shaping breastfeeding decisions, while mobile health technologies and antenatal education have emerged as effective tools to support mothers^v

Exclusive breastfeeding is important for the health of both mother and baby. It provides complete nutrition and protects the baby from infections. However, many mothers do not practice exclusive breastfeeding due to lack of awareness, social pressure, and other personal or environmental factors. In urban areas, mothers face more challenges like work stress and limited family support. This study will help to understand how many mothers are practicing exclusive breastfeeding and what their attitudes are toward it. The findings will help improve awareness and guide future health programs.

MATERIAL & METHODS

A hospital based descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Gynecology, Maternal and Child health Care at Civil Hospital Nawabshah, following approval from the Institutional Review Board. The study was carried out over two months from 17 November to 17 January 2026. A total sample of 188 mothers with infants aged 0-12 months was determined using OpenEpi Info software at a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. Participants were selected through non-probability convenience sampling technique. The inclusion criteria was mothers aged 18-45 years who attended routine follow-up or child healthcare visits and provided informed consent. Mothers with medical conditions affecting breastfeeding, infants with congenital anomalies or feeding disorders and those who refused to participate were excluded.

Data were collected using structured questionnaire adapted from standardized WHO and national survey instruments. The questionnaire comprised three components demographic characteristics, breastfeeding practices and maternal attitudes toward exclusive breastfeeding practices measured using likert scale.

RESULTS

Figure 1: Age of Respondents

Figure 2: Education of Respondents

Table 1: Number of children

No. Of children	Frequency	Percent
Primipara	54	28.7%
Multipara	134	71.3%
Total	188	100.0%

Table 2: Religion of respondents

Religion	Frequency	Percent
Islam	176	93.6%
Hindu	9	4.8%
Christian	3	1.6%
Total	188	100.0%

Figure 3: Age of Respondent's infant

Figure 4: Sex of Respondent's Infant

Table 3: Place of Delivery

Place	Frequency	Percent
Hospital	184	97.9%
Home	4	2.1%
Total	188	100.0%

Table 6: Husband's Occupation

Husbands occupation	Frequency	Percent
Employed	186	98.9%
Unemployed	2	1.1%
Total	188	100.0%

Table 7: Practices

Questions	Yes	No
Did your baby breastfeed yesterday during the day or night	83(44.1%)	104(55.3%)
Did your baby drink plain water yesterday	31(16.5%)	157(83.5%)
Did your baby drink juice, tea, or any other liquids	6(3.2%)	182(96.8%)
Did your baby drink infant formula	94(50.0%)	94(94(50.0%))
Did your baby drink animal milk (cow, goat, buffalo, etc.)	14(7.4)	174(92.6%)
Did your eat any soft/solid foods such as porridge, cereals, or mashed foods	14(7.4%)	174(92.6%)
Did your baby receive ORS, medicines, or vitamin drops	46(22.3%)	146(77.7%)

Table 8: Attitudes

Questions	Wrong	Correct
A baby can survive without water for the first 6 months	9(4.8%)	179(95.2%)
Formula milk is unsuitable for babies	137(72.9%)	51(27.1%)
Formula is not better choice for working mothers	112(59.6%)	75(39.9%)
Breast milk is more easily digested than formula milk.	8(43%)	180(95.7%)
Exclusive breast feeding improves bonding between mother and baby.	3(1.6%)	185(98.4%)
Exclusive breast feeding helps in child growth and development.	4(2.1%)	183(97.3%)
Exclusive breast feeding should be encouraged by health care providers.	4(2.1%)	184(94.9%)
Exclusive breastfeeding is convenient and economical.	5(2.7%)	183(97.3%)

Table 9: Prevalence of Exclusive Breast Feeding

Prevalence of Exclusive Breast Feeding	Frequency	Percent
Yes	50	26.6%
No	138	73.4%
Total	188	100.0%

DISCUSSION

The mean age of the respondents in the present study was 30.38 ± 5.529 years, indicating that most mothers were in the mature reproductive age group. This age range is generally associated with better maternal experience and awareness regarding infant feeding practices. The majority of participants were multiparous (71.3%), which may contribute to improved knowledge and confidence related to breastfeeding, as previous experience often enhances maternal skills.

Most respondents belonged to the Islam religion (93.6%), reflecting the population distribution of the study area. Almost all deliveries (97.9%) occurred in hospitals, suggesting good access to maternal health services. A large proportion of mothers lived in joint families (64.4%), and nearly all respondents (98.4%) reported having family support.

The findings revealed that exclusive breastfeeding practice was suboptimal among one-month mothers. Only 44.1% of infants were breastfed during the previous day or night, while 50% of mothers had introduced formula milk within the first month of life. This indicates a high prevalence of mixed feeding practices. A cross-sectional study in Ethiopia reported that 46.4% of mothers practiced exclusive breastfeeding at one month postpartum, highlighting similar challenges in maintaining exclusive feeding despite policy interventions^{vi}.

Although the intake of plain water (16.5%), animal milk (7.4%), and soft or solid foods (7.4%) was comparatively low, their presence still contradicts the world health organization’s recommendation of exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months. The use of ORS, medicines, or vitamin drops (22.3%) may reflect medical advice; however, it still interrupts strict exclusive breastfeeding in some cases the discrepancy between knowledge and practice in this study indicates several influencing factors. This pattern mirrors findings from Nepal, where early introduction of complementary feeds was attributed

to perceived insufficient milk supply and cultural norms favoring mixed feeding^{vii}.

A vast majority correctly believed that infants can survive without water for the first six months (95.2%). Almost all respondents agreed that exclusive breastfeeding improves bonding (98.4%), supports child growth and development (97.3%), and is convenient and economical (97.3%). Additionally, most mothers (94.9%) felt that exclusive breastfeeding should be encouraged by healthcare providers, highlighting trust in professional guidance. These findings indicate that knowledge and attitude levels were satisfactory among the study population. Similarly, in a 2024 study conducted in urban India, 87% of mothers held positive attitudes toward exclusive breastfeeding, recognizing its health and developmental benefits^{viii}.

A key finding of the present study is the gap between positive attitude and actual breastfeeding practice. Although most mothers were aware of the benefits of exclusive breastfeeding, many introduced formula or other feeds early. Possible reasons include perceived insufficient breast milk, family pressure, convenience, or lack of continued postnatal breastfeeding support. Similar observations WHO Reported that family influence played a significant role in early supplementation despite maternal knowledge^{ix}.

CONCLUSION

This study assessed the prevalence and maternal attitudes toward exclusive breastfeeding among mothers of infants aged 0–12 months. The findings revealed that exclusive breastfeeding practice was suboptimal, with a considerable proportion of mothers introducing formula milk and other feeds within the first month of life. While most mothers showed positive attitudes and good knowledge regarding the benefits of exclusive breastfeeding, these positive perceptions did not fully translate into

practice. The gap between knowledge and actual behavior suggests the influence of other factors such as perceived insufficient milk supply, family influence, cultural beliefs, and lack of continued breastfeeding support.

Regardless of high rates of hospital delivery and reported family support, exclusive breastfeeding

prevalence remains below the recommended level. Therefore, improved breastfeeding counseling, follow-up support, and community-based interventions are necessary to enhance exclusive breastfeeding practices and reduce early supplementation.

REFERENCES

1. Pullum TW, Gribble K, Mirshahi S, Borg B. Estimating the prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding with data from household surveys: Measurement issues and options. *Frontiers in Nutrition*. 2023 Mar 24;10:1058134.
2. Hasan M, Hassan MN, Khan MS, Tareq MA, Afroj MS. Prevalence, knowledge, attitudes and factors associated with exclusive breastfeeding among mothers in Dhaka, Bangladesh: A cross-sectional study. *Population Medicine*. 2021 Sep 7;3(September):1-7.
3. Ghafoor EA, Zafar T, Muqadas S, Zubair A, Majeed FA, Majeed T. Prevalence of exclusive breast breeding in postnatal ward at central park teaching hospital. *The Professional Medical Journal*. 2025 Sep 4;32(09):1155-61.
4. Ghaffar Y. Knowledge, attitude, utilization frequency, and reutilization of telehealth centers for maternal care services among pregnant women and mothers in Pakistan: a cross-sectional study.
5. Munawar K, Mukhtar F, Roy M, Majeed N, Jalaludin MY. A systematic review of parenting and feeding practices, children's feeding behavior and growth stunting in Asian countries. *Psychology, Health & Medicine*. 2024 Nov 25;29(10):1705-52.
6. Srinivasan M, Mathew G, Mathew N, Kumar M, Goyal N, Kamath MS. Technologies that empower women for better access to healthcare in IndiaA scoping review. *Global Public Health*. 2024 Dec 31;19(1):2318240.
7. Manapurath R, Veetil DR, Kamath MS. Use of modern technologies for promoting health at the population level in India. *The Lancet Regional Health-Southeast Asia*. 2024 Apr 1;23.
8. Setegn T, Belachew T, Gerbaba M, Deribe K, Deribew A, Biadgilign S. Factors associated with exclusive breastfeeding practices among mothers in Goba district, south east Ethiopia: a cross-sectional study. *International breastfeeding journal*. 2012 Nov 27;7(1):17.
9. Karki R, Joshi S, Kaphle M. Complementary Feeding